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Self-rated health among students at a Brazilian university during the Covid-19 pandemic

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ABSTRACT

Introduction: The covid-19 pandemic has impacted teaching-learning and healthcare practices at universities. The relationships between health and training processes in higher education require understanding the different aspects related to the lives of university students. **Objective:** This study aimed to describe self-rated health among students at a Brazilian university during the covid-19 pandemic. **Methodology:** This is qualitative research. Semi-structured interviews produced data with students of interdisciplinary courses in arts, science and technology, humanities, and health. These data were analyzed according to content analysis and submitted to Descending Hierarchical Classification in *Interface de R pour les Analyses Multidimensionnelles de Textes et de Questionnaires*. **Results:** Self-rated health among the 33 participating students emphasized the components of mental and physical health and illness (first class of Descending Hierarchical Classification), university life and coronavirus prevention strategies (second class), and lifestyle (third class). In this sense, illness, difficulties in remote learning, and a sedentary lifestyle contributed to a negative self-perception of health status. At the same time, when positive, the health self-assessment was based on the absence of health problems, adherence to preventive practices, return to in-person academic activities, and healthy lifestyle habits. **Conclusion:** Students' self-rated health combines factors associated with academic life, experiences, concepts, and practices of health and illness in the covid-19 pandemic, reinforcing the relevance of qualifying care towards the development of healthy learning spaces.

KEYWORDS

Health. Mental health. University students. Higher education.

Autoavaliação da saúde de estudantes de uma universidade brasileira durante a pandemia Covid-19

RESUMO

Introdução: A pandemia covid-19 gerou impactos diversos nas práticas de ensino-aprendizagem e cuidado em saúde na universidade. As relações entre a saúde e os processos formativos na educação superior suscitam a necessidade de compreensão dos diferentes aspectos relacionados à vida de estudantes universitários. **Objetivo:** Objetivou-se descrever a autoavaliação da saúde de estudantes de uma universidade brasileira durante a pandemia covid-19. **Metodologia:** Trata-se de uma pesquisa qualitativa, com dados produzidos através de entrevistas semiestruturadas com discentes de cursos interdisciplinares na área de artes, ciência e tecnologia, humanidades e saúde. Esses dados foram analisados conforme a análise de conteúdo e submetidos à Classificação Hierárquica Descendente (CHD) na *Interface de R pour les Analyses Multidimensionnelles de Textes et de Questionnaires*. **Resultados:** A autoavaliação da saúde dos 33 estudantes participantes enfatizou os componentes da saúde e adoecimento mental e físico (classe 1 da CHD), da vida universitária e medidas de prevenção ao coronavírus (classe 2), e do estilo de vida (classe 3). Nesse sentido, o adoecimento, as dificuldades no ensino remoto e o sedentarismo colaboraram com uma autopercepção negativa do estado de saúde. Ao mesmo tempo, quando positiva, a autoavaliação da saúde foi fundamentada na inexistência de problemas de saúde, adesão às práticas preventivas, retorno das atividades acadêmicas presenciais e hábitos de vida saudáveis. **Conclusão:** A autoavaliação da saúde desses estudantes combina fatores relacionados à vida acadêmica, experiências, concepções e práticas de saúde e adoecimento na pandemia covid-19, reiterando a relevância de qualificação do cuidado no sentido do desenvolvimento de ambientes de aprendizagem saudáveis.

PALAVRAS-CHAVE

Saúde. Saúde mental. Estudante universitário. Educação superior.

Autoevaluación de la salud de los estudiantes de una universidad brasileña durante la pandemia del Covid-19

RESUMEN

Introducción: La pandemia del covid-19 impactó en las prácticas de enseñanza y aprendizaje, y en la atención a la salud en la universidad. Las relaciones entre salud y procesos de formación requieren comprender los diferentes aspectos de la vida de los estudiantes universitarios. **Objetivo:** El objetivo fue describir la autoevaluación de la salud de los estudiantes de una universidad brasileña durante la pandemia del covid-19. **Metodología:** Se trata de una investigación cualitativa, con datos producidos mediante entrevistas semiestructuradas a estudiantes de cursos interdisciplinares de artes, ciencia y tecnología, humanidades y salud. Estos datos se analizaron mediante análisis de contenido y Clasificación Jerárquica Descendente en la *Interface de R pour les Analyses Multidimensionnelles de Textes et de Questionnaires*. **Resultados:** La autoevaluación de la salud de los 33 estudiantes se centró en los componentes de salud y enfermedad (primera clase de la Clasificación Jerárquica Descendente), la vida universitaria y las medidas de prevención (segunda clase), y el estilo de vida (tercera clase). La enfermedad, las dificultades para la enseñanza a distancia y el sedentarismo contribuyeron a una autopercepción negativa de la salud. Cuando fue positiva, se basó en la ausencia de problemas de salud, la adherencia a prácticas preventivas, el retorno a las actividades académicas presenciales y los hábitos de vida saludables. **Conclusión:** La autoevaluación de la salud de los estudiantes combina factores relacionados con la vida académica, concepciones y prácticas de salud y enfermedad en la pandemia del covid-19, lo que reitera la relevancia del desarrollo de entornos de aprendizaje saludables.

PALABRAS CLAVE

Salud. Salud mental. Estudiante universitario. Educación superior.

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Introduction

Health is a social good that affects all aspects of life. The relationship between health and educational processes in higher education has been highlighted in various studies, with emphasis on the impact of health-related problems on academic performance and university life as a whole (Amaral; Frick, 2023; Gomes *et al.*, 2023; Gundim *et al.*, 2022; Vieira; Torrenté, 2022). Studying and promoting the health of university students, in a broader sense, is an important task for educators. In this sense, Vieira and Torrenté (2022, p. 13) highlighted the need for universities to advance the debate on their responsibility in "building healthy beings".

The COVID-19 pandemic has been described as a period that has marked the history of humanity in terms of its far-reaching impact on human life. It has certainly been one of the greatest global challenges of our time, as it has led to major health, social, cultural, educational, political, and economic changes and adaptations, not just a simple collection of strategies to combat the spread of SARS-CoV-2. Climate change, the deterioration of social life, the resurgence of capitalist/neoliberal mechanisms of oppression and exploitation, and the deepening of inequalities rooted in colonialist systems of subalternization draw our attention to the need to assess health, illness, care and death, without forgetting the crises associated with them and their impact on the vulnerability of different social groups (Nunes, 2020).

In the educational sector, the social distancing, restriction, and isolation measures triggered by the rapid spread of COVID-19 have resulted in the closure of university campuses and an abrupt transition to distance education. These changes have had a direct impact on the university community, as evidenced by the studies carried out with students, which highlight the various effects of the COVID-19 pandemic on health and quality of life. The conditions related to the continuity of studies and other academic activities, the fear of contracting the acute respiratory syndrome caused by SARS-CoV-2, withdrawal from friends and teachers, and social isolation were some of the factors that caused depressive symptoms, stress, anxiety, changes in sleep patterns, fear and worry among university students (Abbas *et al.*, 2022; Arar *et al.*, 2023; Gundim *et al.*, 2022; Hotta *et al.*, 2023; Menegaldi-Silva *et al.*, 2022; Miotto *et al.*, 2022; Oliveira *et al.*, 2022; Ramos *et al.*, 2023; Rogowska *et al.*, 2021; Yuan *et al.*, 2023).

This study adds to the research that has been conducted with university students in the context of the pandemic (Abbas *et al.*, 2022; Arar *et al.*, 2023; Gundim *et al.*, 2022; Hotta *et al.*, 2023; Menegaldi-Silva *et al.*, 2022; Miotto *et al.*, 2022; Oliveira *et al.*, 2022; Ramos *et al.*, 2023; Rogowska *et al.*, 2021; Yuan *et al.*, 2023). Considering that the impact of the COVID-19 pandemic did not end with the end of the public health emergency, as we are still living with its effects on contemporary lifestyles and health (and we don't know when), there is a need to continue producing knowledge about this still recent historical moment.

The new variants of the virus, the collective efforts to achieve vaccination goals, the readjustment to "face-to-face" life, the educational activities in a hybrid model, the unacceptable levels of poverty and hunger, aggravated by the lack of effective social protection, among other issues, all materialize the reverberations of that period in everyday life today. In Brazil, some of these factors were aggravated by the fact that the pandemic situation required a balance between maintaining the operating conditions of the public health network and political-governmental disputes over the implementation, suspension, or rejection of health measures, which led universities and research centers to take a stand in defense of research and preventive measures (Bosi; Alves, 2023), even in the face of significant budget cuts, in a movement to fight for the Unified Health System. In this sense, there are still questions to be answered about the health of segments of the Brazilian population in the COVID-19 pandemic, such as university students.

From this perspective, this study aims to describe the self-rated health of students at a Brazilian university during the COVID-19 pandemic. In line with attempts to define health from the experiences of the subjects (Batistella, 2007; Mendonça; Lanza, 2021; Silva; Schraiber; Mota, 2019), self-rated health was used (Fayers; Sprangers, 2002; Fylkesnes; Jakobsen; Henriksen, 2021; Jylhä, 2009) to understand the health status of these university students based on their voices.

During the first wave of the COVID-19 pandemic, in a survey of students from educational institutions in nine countries, 90.25% rated their health as excellent, very good or good, while 9.75% rated it as fair or poor (Rogowska *et al.*, 2021). In a survey of students in southeastern Brazil between September 2020 and January 2021, 67.3% rated their health as good or very good and 32.7% as fair or poor (Ramos *et al.*, 2023). This research takes a fresh look at the issue by studying health from a qualitative perspective and with students from courses in four major areas of knowledge, covering the different moments of the pandemic, including the most intense social isolation and the resumption of face-to-face activities with the relaxation of some health measures. Understanding how students perceive their health is fundamental for the development of health strategies and interventions targeted at this audience to collaborate with institutional policies and promote healthier and more resilient learning environments, contributing to the well-being of the university community.

Methodology

This is a descriptive qualitative study. Self-rated health is a construct that is widely used in research and interventions with the aim of collecting and synthesizing information about the health of individuals (Fayers; Sprangers, 2002; Fylkesnes; Jakobsen; Henriksen, 2021; Jylhä, 2009). In surveys, respondents are asked to make an analytical effort to construct a self-image of their state of health. In this analysis, the dimensions of the physical, mental, social, and cultural body are crossed with aspects related to living conditions and lifestyles, well-being, quality of life, knowledge, health beliefs and practices, resources available for

care, access to the health system, experiences of illness, suffering, and healing, race, gender, social class, age group, and other social markers of difference, according to the experiences and perceptions of each person. Therefore, considering the ways of life that permeate and are permeated by social, economic, and cultural contexts, self-assessment can reveal the determining and conditioning elements of health in a given time and space, while at the same time expressing an individual's particular understanding of health, as each person follows a particular path to define their state of health (Jylhä, 2009).

Data were collected through semi-structured interviews between November 2021 and October 2022. For these interviews, a semi-structured script developed by the authors was used, consisting of questions about the participants' sociodemographic information, illness experiences, care pathways, and self-assessment of health during the COVID-19 pandemic.

The group of participants defined for the research were students of the Interdisciplinary Baccalaureate in Arts, Science and Technology, Humanities, and Health at the Federal University of Bahia. The Interdisciplinary Baccalaureate is an undergraduate program that differs from others in that it integrates a comprehensive humanistic, scientific, and artistic education with in-depth studies in a specific field of knowledge. It was born out of a proposal for university reform that sought to establish a system of university education in cycles, with the interdisciplinary bachelor's degree as the first cycle, professional undergraduate courses as the second cycle, and postgraduate studies as the third cycle. This model has been implemented in different Brazilian universities, but coexists with the conventional curricular architecture, in which the entry to higher education is made through an early decision to take a professional course (Teixeira; Coelho; Rocha, 2013).

The decision to conduct the research with students from interdisciplinary bachelor programs was motivated by two reasons. Firstly, because these courses are related to different fields of knowledge, ensuring the participation of students from different fields of knowledge. Secondly, because the interdisciplinary bachelor's degree is a new type of academic degree in Brazil, which demonstrates the need to produce data on the population that takes it. This type, of course, has some peculiarities that can mobilize specific experiences related to health and teaching and learning processes in higher education, such as having curricula based on interdisciplinarity and having a student body that, for the most part, goes through an internal selection process at the university with the aim of moving to another stage of training at the end of the first cycle (Teixeira; Coelho; Rocha, 2013).

Students were invited to participate in the interviews by contacting the researchers via institutional email and university social networks. The inclusion criteria for the study were to be a student in one of the four interdisciplinary undergraduate programs (Arts, Science and Technology, Humanities, or Health) and to be 18 years of age or older. At the time of data collection, the university was going through a period of resumption of face-to-face academic activities, including undergraduate classes. As a result, some interviews were conducted face-to-face and others remotely. In the case of the face-to-face interviews, we would like to point out that they were conducted in an airy environment, with distance between people and the

use of a mask and hand sanitizer, in accordance with the safety protocols associated with COVID-19.

A total of 35 interviews were conducted, but two were excluded. One was due to a problem with the student participant's internet connection, which meant that the interview could not be completed. The other was excluded because, at the time of its completion, the student participant informed us that she had just transferred to a second cycle course, having recently completed her interdisciplinary bachelor's degree.

The interview script consisted of open-ended questions and allowed the interviewees to discuss the research topic without being bound by the questions asked (Minayo, 2014). For the purposes of this article, we only considered the excerpts that dealt with self-assessment of health. To start the conversation on this topic, students were asked how they assessed their health during the COVID-19 pandemic, covering the period of social isolation and the return to face-to-face activities.

At the end of data production, the interviews were transcribed and analyzed using content analysis (Bardin, 2016). In the analysis process, the responses were first read to become familiar with their content and to build the textual corpus. The corpus was then subjected to Descending Hierarchical Classification (DHC) in the R Interface for Multidimensional Text and Questionnaire Analyses (IRaMuTeQ). DHC (Reinert's method) is an analysis method that produces groupings (classes) of text segments with similar vocabularies, according to the co-occurrences recorded between the lexical forms (terms that make up the corpus). Characteristically, the classes are stable in the sense that they contrast with each other but have a high degree of internal homogeneity. When processing the corpus in IRaMuTeQ, the Chi-square test is used to define the degree of association between the terms and the classes to which they belong. The results are presented in the form of a dendrogram, which shows the classes together with the most representative terms in each class (Oliveira; Gomes; Marques, 2005; Sousa, 2021). In this study, DHC produced three classes with a total usage of 89.43% of the text segments in the processed material.

The interpretation of the data was based on the identification of the content underlying the classes, bearing in mind that the set of lexical forms and text segments that make them up express a certain idea about the object under study (Oliveira; Gomes; Marques, 2005; Sousa, 2021). In this way, it was assumed that the statements obtained in the interviews, organized through text segments in lexical classes, refer to different contexts and experiences of health-illness-care in the COVID-19 pandemic, revealing different aspects of health self-evaluation.

This work is part of the research project "Remote teaching in the COVID-19 pandemic: social representations and practices of university students", which focuses on understanding the scenarios generated by the COVID-19 pandemic, remote teaching, social isolation, and the return to face-to-face activities in the university student community. The project was approved by the Research Ethics Committee of the School of Nursing of the Federal University of Bahia (Opinion No. 5.050.672). To ensure anonymity of participation,

the names of rivers flowing through Brazilian communities were used to describe the students involved in this study.

Results

Of the 33 participants, 16 (48.49%) identified as cisgender men, 15 as cisgender women (45.45%), and two as non-binary transgender (6.06%). In terms of race/color, 23 (69.70%) students identified as black and 10 (30.3%) identified as white. The majority of these students were not working for pay in person or from home (25 - 75.76%) or receiving affirmative action/student aid (29 - 87.88%) at the time of the survey, while smaller proportions were working (8 - 24.24%) or receiving this type of aid (4 - 12.12%). The majority (48.48% - 16) of the students had no religion; 6 (18.19%) were Evangelicals, 5 (15.15%) were Catholics, 3 (9.09%) were Candomblecists and 3 (9.09%) were related to other religions. At university, 10 (30.3%) were enrolled in the interdisciplinary bachelor's degree in humanities, 10 (30.3%) in health, 7 (21.22%) in arts, and 6 (18.18%) in science and technology (Table 1).

Table 1. Profile of survey participants, Salvador (BA), 2021-2022 (n = 33)

Gender	N°	%
Cisgender man	16	48,49%
Cisgender woman	15	45,45%
Non-binary	2	6,06%
Race/color	N°	%
Black	23	69,70%
White	10	30,30%
Religion	N°	%
No religion	16	48,48%
Evangelical	6	18,19%
Catholic	5	15,15%
Candomblé	3	9,09%
Other religion	3	9,09%
Paid work	N°	%
Yes	8	24,24%
No	25	75,76%
Beneficiary of financial aid for affirmative action/student assistance	N°	%
Yes	4	12,12%
No	29	87,88%
Course	N°	%
Interdisciplinary bachelor's degree in health	10	30,30%
Interdisciplinary bachelor's degree in humanities	10	30,30%
Interdisciplinary bachelor's degree in arts	7	21,22%
Interdisciplinary bachelor's degree in science and technology	6	18,18%

Source: Own authorship.

These students' self-assessed health during the COVID-19 pandemic showed that they valued components of mental and physical health and illness (class 1), university life and coronavirus prevention measures (class 2), and lifestyle (class 3). Figure 1 shows the DHC dendrogram with the most representative terms and the socio-demographic characteristics most associated with each class. As with the terms, the socio-demographic characteristics were distributed across the classes according to the highest degree of association calculated in the DHC processing, so that the same characteristic was not duplicated in more than one class. Similarly, some categories of socio-demographic characteristics are not represented in all classes because they were not associated with all classes.

Figure 1. Components of university students' self-rated health during the COVID-19 pandemic, Salvador (BA), 2021-2022

Source: Own authorship.

Caption: ST - text segments; SUS - Unified Health System.

Class 1 concentrated on 146 text segments (35.96%) of the DHC. The most representative term in this class is "health," which also had the highest chi-square in the analysis ($\chi^2= 81.997$). However, even though "health" has the highest degree of association with the statements of the participants who constitute the class, the general lines of self-rated health are not guided by its isolated analysis. In most of its appearances, the term refers to the health-illness process in a generalized way, without delimiting a positive or negative meaning associated with self-rated health. This meaning is constructed from the content that accompanies and complements the term. The socio-demographic characteristics most associated with the class were being cisgender or non-binary, being black, having no religion or being Candomblecist, being enrolled in the Interdisciplinary Bachelor's degree in Science and Technology, and not receiving affirmative action or student aid.

This class emphasizes the mental and physical dimensions as constitutive of health. In the responses, there is a distinction between what is "mental" (individual psychological processes) and what is "physical" (individual biological processes). Thus, although they are listed as part of the production of the same state of health, there is a difference between treating mental health and physical health as two entities that are connected or not. For example, in Rio Jacuí's account (cisgender, black male, interdisciplinary bachelor of arts), mental suffering didn't seem to produce a relationship with the physical dimension of health: "But in terms of mental health, it's...there were days when I was just living, surviving, you know? I existed; I did things for the sake of doing things, but that's it. But in terms of my physical health, I think it's good". In contrast, the statement of Rio Jaguaribe (non-binary, white, interdisciplinary bachelor of health) heralds a circumstance in which the influence of mental health on physical health is manifested: "I see myself as much more... much safer with my mental health, for example. I have more tact with it; I have more power over things. And that also affects my physical health".

In one way or another, for some students, a good self-assessment of health was determined by the absence of illness and other problems, while a poor self-assessment considered the continuity of existing problems before the COVID-19 pandemic and the development of new problems during this period. In the participants' statements, "problem" is used to refer directly to illness, as in "health problem", but it also includes social and financial issues that make life challenging.

I usually never say that I'm not completely healthy because I always have some problem to talk about. But this time, I really don't think I have any. [...] For the first time, I'm feeling good, both physically and mentally. (Rio Uruguai, cisgender man, black, interdisciplinary bachelor's degree in humanities)

I think my health was in chaos. There was no way... I only saw problems everywhere, I only saw things that I couldn't cope with. (Rio São Francisco, cisgender woman, black, interdisciplinary bachelor's degree in humanities)

Among other things, a good self-assessment of health was related to the ability to deal with problems, understanding that it is possible to feel healthy even in the presence of them:

“I think that during the pandemic, despite the worries [...] we can have some kind of problem and still feel healthy. In general, I feel that I managed to get through the pandemic healthy” (Rio Madeira, cisgender woman, black, interdisciplinary bachelor's degree in health). In the same vein of thinking about health beyond the absence of illness, the idea that health is made up of different components was associated with difficulty in making a more positive self-assessment of health status: “I think my health could be better. In what way? I think health is not just the absence of disease. Health is a whole complex, right? The psychic, the physical, the mental, the spiritual” (Rio Solimões, cisgender male, white, interdisciplinary bachelor in health).

Anxiety, depressive symptoms, aggravation of chronic diseases, pain in different parts of the body, respiratory syndromes, and post-covid-19 sequelae are among the symptoms and processes of illness mentioned in the students' responses. They reported consulting health professionals for diagnostic and therapeutic purposes, especially medical and psychological professionals. An interesting issue pointed out by the students was the fear of going to health institutions during social isolation because of the possibility of contamination by COVID-19.

Yes, the pandemic affected me a little, but the fact that I was in therapy helped a lot. That's why I said I didn't have a giant increase in anxiety, for example, which is one of the problems I have because I was being monitored (Rio Araguaia, cisgender woman, black, interdisciplinary bachelor in humanities).

And I was also terrified, so much so that now I'm resuming medical care because I was afraid of catching COVID, right? And going to the hospital and catching COVID wasn't something I wanted to do either, now that I feel more comfortable going out, and I'm... trying to do all my exams (Rio Juruá, cisgender man, black, interdisciplinary bachelor of arts).

Class 2 contains 36.45% (148) of the text segments in the analysis, highlighting university life during social isolation, the return to face-to-face activities, and preventive measures related to SARS-CoV-2. Although this is the largest lexical class in the research, as it contains the largest number of text segments, we observed that its main terms have lower chi-squared values compared to the other classes, which may indicate little stability or internal homogeneity in the class. The sociodemographic characteristics most associated with this class were being a cisgender woman, being white, enrolled in an interdisciplinary bachelor's degree in the humanities or arts, having a paid job, and receiving aid from affirmative action or student aid. "University" ($\chi^2 = 17.221$) is the term most associated with the class, with concerns about academic progress and study routines during distance education cited as factors negatively affecting health. On the other hand, face-to-face university activities were seen as beneficial to health, including classes and contact with people on campus. However, there were also difficulties in returning to face-to-face academic activities, given the need to re-adapt to face-to-face teaching and the change of residence for students who returned to their home cities in social isolation.

After college classes resumed, I felt much more. How can I put it? Encouraged to keep going and finish my degree and move on to the next one. Also observing my surroundings. [...] In distance learning, in this case, we don't have that physical contact, so it feels like we're alone. [...] The classes are back, and the contact is

back; I think it's improved a lot (Rio Branco, cisgender woman, black, interdisciplinary bachelor's degree in arts).
 [...] and because of all the uncertainty that comes with going back to class and what it's going to be like, having to move back to the capital, having to move again, having to go back, and so on and so forth, all these processes (Rio Solimões, cisgender man, white, interdisciplinary bachelor's degree in health).

For these participants, the methodology used in the selection process for the transition from the interdisciplinary bachelor's degree to the professional courses in the second cycle was another factor that adversely affected their state of health, as Rio Tietê says when she expresses her concern about achieving a certain score to enter the psychology course: "And in the IB [Interdisciplinary Bachelor's Degree], in a way I have to worry a lot about my score because I want to go into psychology. [...] So I end up organizing my routine around that worry" (cisgender woman, white, interdisciplinary bachelor's degree in humanities).

In terms of coronavirus prevention measures, participants mentioned wearing a mask and social isolation, indicating that they contributed positively to health in terms of protection against COVID-19 acute respiratory syndrome and other respiratory infections. Although social isolation was considered beneficial as a means of limiting the spread of the coronavirus, it was also described as a health-damaging measure because it alienates people and reduces social interaction.

So, I think in a way, on the one hand, it improved a little bit because I didn't go out, I didn't have much contact with people I knew, with people on buses, on public transportation, that kind of thing, no... and also with the use of the mask and everything and other precautions, I think that helped as well (Rio Amazonas, cisgender woman, black, interdisciplinary bachelor's degree in arts).
 I don't think the isolation helped much. At the time, I used to say that isolation was fine, that I didn't care much about it, and so on. But after a while, I realized the effect of constant isolation, right? (Rio Jiquiriçá, cisgender woman, white, interdisciplinary bachelor's degree in arts).

However, complete adherence to social isolation was not a reality for all the research participants. Rio Tapajós, for example, worked in person during the dramatic moments of the pandemic: "Even at the peak, even going out, working every day, in contact with several other people, some who even had COVID-19, were diagnosed [...]" (cisgender male, white, interdisciplinary bachelor in science and technology).

Students also reported adherence to the vaccination and said that this practice helped to alleviate their social isolation, allowing them to return to face-to-face activities and meetings with friends: "I had an improvement to the extent that there was some flexibility, you know, with the progress of the vaccine. So, for example, I was able to go out and meet with the boys right after the vaccine" (Rio São Francisco, cisgender woman, black, interdisciplinary bachelor's degree in humanities). In this sense, the reduction in the number of SARS-CoV-2 infections and the easing of social isolation were viewed positively by the students.

The third class includes the text segments (112 - 27.59%) that characterize the

influence of lifestyle on health. The most representative socio-demographic categories in this class are: being an interdisciplinary bachelor of health student, Evangelical, Catholic, affiliated with other religions, and not working. It should be noted that gender, race/color, and involvement in student aid or affirmative action were not related to this class in the DHC because they were not strongly associated with it. According to the responses, positive self-assessment of health was defined by healthy eating, physical activity, body weight control, and adequate water consumption, habits that for many students were started during the COVID-19 pandemic, as is the case of Rio Paraná (cisgender woman, black, interdisciplinary bachelor in health), who began to pay more attention to eating during this period. On the other hand, negative self-rated health was associated with an unfavorable lifestyle that developed or intensified during social isolation and was characterized by an unhealthy diet, sedentary lifestyle, overweight/obesity and low water consumption:

[...] I gained weight during the pandemic. [...] It's because I lost weight, right? I've lost weight, and when I lose weight, I feel better and everything. I know I'm reducing many risks (Rio Xingu, cisgender male, black, interdisciplinary bachelor's degree in arts).

I used to be... sedentary. It's... I think my health situation was terrible because I've always taken care of my health and... Physical activity, practicing physical activity, and eating well. And during the pandemic, not only did I not eat well, but I didn't do any physical activity, so I think my health was very compromised. (Rio Doce, cisgender male, black, interdisciplinary bachelor's degree in health).

As we have seen, the self-rated health of the students participating in this research was analyzed based on three classes: mental and physical health and illness (class 1), university life and coronavirus prevention measures (class 2), and lifestyle (class 3). The students' statements, presented through the classes, relate this self-assessment to elements present within and outside the routines of higher education in the COVID-19 pandemic. These findings are discussed in the next section.

Discussion

As a complex global phenomenon of major proportions for the organization of society, the COVID-19 pandemic has presented a series of challenges in different aspects of life and collective health. In the DHC of the self-assessment of health of the students participating in this research, the points related to health and illness at the mental and physical level (class 1), university life and coronavirus prevention measures (class 2) and lifestyle (class 3) stood out, revealing that the process of determining the state of health of these university students involved the intersection of conceptions of health, experiences of illness and care, study, work, preventive practices, lifestyle habits, desires, concerns, routines, social behaviors and interpersonal relationships shaped in the pandemic scenario. Knowing that different orientations and understandings of the object of health coexist in contemporary times (Batistella, 2007; Mendonça; Lanza, 2021; Scliar, 2007; Silva; Schraiber; Mota, 2019), these results explain the specificities of students in interdisciplinary bachelor's programs through the issues they ponder as part of the production of their health in the new coronavirus

pandemic.

Recognizing the mental and physical dimensions in determining the state of health points to a conception guided by an interpretive and practical bias toward integration between different phenomena in the health-disease process, characteristic of a biopsychosocial perspective (Batistella, 2007). This perspective collaborates with efforts to direct a more attentive view to mental health care, considering a broader critique of biomedicine as the exclusive study of the physical-biological body (Carmargo Jr., 2005; Guimarães *et al.*, 2020). The inclusion of mental health among the components of these students' self-assessment of their health also confirms the health situation of the COVID-19 pandemic, in which the psychological suffering caused by social isolation, fear, illness, and death mediated sudden changes in daily life and inequalities that highlighted mental health needs (Bosi; Alves, 2023). As we have seen since the conceptualization of health by the World Health Organization (Batistella, 2007; Scliar, 2007; Silva; Schraiber; Mota, 2019), multidimensional proposals to approach health have reached the political, theoretical, and conceptual debate and are currently competing for space in public policies and health services.

On the other hand, the demarcation and framing of life events into watertight and closed categories in the mental and physical spheres, as well as a fragmented treatment of the relationship between these dimensions, imprints the mind-body dichotomy as part of the cosmology and anatomy of biomedical rationality (Carmargo Jr., 2005). From a dichotomous perspective, a view of health as the absence of disease was also reproduced among the students who participated in this research. In line with biomedical interpretations of the human body, the opposition between health and illness has been widely described since the definition of standards of normality in biostatistical and functional terms (Batistella, 2007; Scliar, 2007). Within this logic, the maintenance of a routine of medical consultations and periodic examinations is one of the measures adopted in health care, as noted in previous research conducted with interdisciplinary bachelor students (Coelho *et al.*, 2016). In another direction, we also found among the participants in this research the presence of a concept of health that emphasizes the possibility of feeling healthy even in the course of adversities represented by illness, a perspective that is close to antagonistic approaches to the biomedical concept of health focused on illness, as developed by Canguilhem (1995).

However, it is the concept of health as the absence of disease that dominates contemporary discourses that circulate in common sense (Batistella, 2007), which can be considered linked to colonialism in the field of health, which has led to the erasure of knowledge and practices that do not meet the validation criteria of Western medicine (Guimarães *et al.*, 2020).

The role of illness in self-rated health has been reported in other studies in terms of illness experience, coping, or adaptation (Jylhä, 2009). In the Brazilian population, living with chronic diseases, sleep problems, and chronic low back pain were associated with worse self-rated health in the COVID-19 pandemic (Szwarcwald *et al.*, 2021). Data from a national health survey before the pandemic period already showed a greater association between a

diagnosis of at least one chronic condition and self-rated health as poor or destitute in this population (Szwarcwald *et al.*, 2015), suggesting that students in this study followed a sociocultural trend of using illness to define health status. During the COVID-19 pandemic, social distancing was recognized as a determinant of biopsychosocial problems (Bosi; Alves, 2023), with an association between adherence to social restrictive measures and worsening health status (Szwarcwald *et al.*, 2021). Among the problems reported during this period are feelings of anxiety, sadness, restlessness (Gil *et al.*, 2022), and loneliness (Szwarcwald *et al.*, 2021). More specifically, among university students, common mental disorders (Arar *et al.*, 2023; Gundim *et al.*, 2022), anxiety, and depression (Hotta *et al.*, 2023; Miotto *et al.*, 2022; Ramos *et al.*, 2023; Yuan *et al.*, 2023) have been described as intervening health factors.

In relation to sociodemographic characteristics, other studies have indicated that women and non-white people tend to accumulate more negative percentages of self-perceived health (Andrade; Azeredo; Peres, 2020; Sousa *et al.*, 2020; Szwarcwald *et al.*, 2015, 2021) and that having a religion can act as a protective factor in some states of mental suffering (Menegaldi-Silva *et al.*, 2022). In this study, mental and physical illness was more prevalent among male, non-binary, black, non-religious, and candomblecist students, suggesting that the COVID-19 pandemic may have created a more pronounced experience of illness in this group. An intersectional perspective recognizes the contribution of different structures of oppression to the formation of social identities and the production of illness. In this way, intersectional inequalities and oppressions influence the conditions and events that potentiate the mental suffering of students before or after they enter university (Vieira; Torrenté, 2022).

In this scenario, looking at illness at university highlights the importance of services and practices aimed at promoting the health of the academic community, such as the actions aimed at welcoming students at the Center for Comprehensive Student Health Care at the Federal University of Bahia (Vieira; Torrenté, 2022) and mental health interventions for students at the Federal University of Alagoas (Gomes *et al.*, 2023).

Life at university was another aspect that influenced students' self-rated health, confirming the correlation found between academic engagement and positive mental health among students at a university in southern Brazil (Amaral; Frick, 2023). According to the participants in our study, studying at a distance was surrounded by worries about the future and had a negative impact on their health, while returning to face-to-face activities was considered positive in terms of resuming social interaction and academic training in its traditional format. Other studies have shown that social distancing led to uncertainty about continuing their education and damage to relationships with colleagues and friends at university (Hotta *et al.*, 2023; Rogowska *et al.*, 2021), reinforcing the impact of the sudden change in university routine on students' lives. In the same way that the adherence to distance education triggered the need for the academic community to adapt to the use of information and communication technologies in teaching and learning activities, the difficulties pointed out by students in this research upon their return to face-to-face teaching, such as the readjustment of routines, show us that this period could have triggered a new edition of the process of belonging to university life (Coulon, 2017). In this sense, we could think of a

virtual/remote university life and another face-to-face university life.

In this sense, it is important to note that students who received affirmative action or student aid were more likely to be associated with the DHC course that included university-related questions. Considering that poverty is a social marker of difference attributed to higher rates of unfavorable self-rated health (Sousa *et al.*, 2020; Szwarcwald *et al.*, 2021), this may indicate that distance education and return in person were also moments of dispute over the conditions of permanence at the university among poorer students, causing a greater repercussion of academic life on the health of these students.

One of the concerns related to academic training expressed by the participants concerns access to second-cycle professional courses at the end of the interdisciplinary bachelor's degree. In previous studies, this concern has been found in the trajectories of students of the interdisciplinary bachelor's degree in health, due to the conflicts and tensions in the selection for admission to medical courses (Santos; Almeida Filho, 2016). Therefore, the association of the class with this idea with students of the interdisciplinary bachelor's degree in arts and humanities is noteworthy. This result indicates the need to investigate the impact of the methodology of the selection process for the transition between the first and second cycle in other interdisciplinary bachelor's programs, given that the suffering associated with academic training may have increased proportionally in the context of the COVID-19 pandemic.

Considering that government policies have influenced health-related risks in pandemic scenarios (Abbas *et al.*, 2022), we observed good adherence to coronavirus protection practices among the participants in this study, amidst the wave of scientific denialism and inequalities in coping with COVID-19 (Bosi; Alves, 2023; Nunes, 2020). In the case of DHC, having a job may have been associated with the course that covered these preventive measures due to exposure to coronavirus in face-to-face work activities. A survey of students from Slovenia, the Czech Republic, Germany, Poland, Ukraine, Russia, Turkey, Israel, and Colombia showed that 68.67% were exposed to SARS-CoV-2 (Rogowska *et al.*, 2021). The other sociodemographic characteristic associated with this class was being a cisgender woman. Given that fear of COVID-19 contamination was higher among female students in another study (Oliveira *et al.*, 2022), women may have been more adherent to coronavirus prevention practices, which may have been motivated by representations of care associated with this gender. As the participants in this study attributed a positive impact on their health to the use of these practices, and another study found lower adherence to preventive measures among undergraduate and graduate students who self-rated their health as unhealthy (Hotta *et al.*, 2023), there might have been some agreement on the benefits of using preventive practices within the academic community.

Similarly, the relationship found in this study between positive self-rated health and healthy lifestyle habits is supported by studies that have analyzed self-rated health in different groups (Andrade; Azeredo; Peres, 2020; Hotta *et al.*, 2023; Szwarcwald *et al.*, 2015, 2021). For example, in the Brazilian population, healthy diet and physical activity have been

identified as factors that positively influence self-rated health, while alcohol consumption, smoking, and a sedentary lifestyle lead to greater negative self-rated health (Andrade; Azeredo; Peres, 2020; Szwarcwald *et al.*, 2015, 2021).

If, on the one hand, healthy eating and physical activity provide a good health assessment, it should be noted that a focus on lifestyle can reinforce individual responsibility for one's state of health and override the historical, social, and cultural determination that runs through the health-disease process and even define the possibilities of using these practices (Batistella, 2007). Lifestyle was the most important component of self-rated health for part of the interdisciplinary bachelor's degree students in health, religious students, and those who did not work during the COVID-19 pandemic, which may reflect a greater concern with prescribed health norms among students who have more contact with them in health disciplines or more time available to use "healthy" health practices among students who did not work. In this sense, other studies involving students from interdisciplinary bachelor's degrees in health have also considered lifestyle as one of the determinants of illness (Coelho *et al.*, 2016; Amorim; Coelho; Rocha, 2021).

Final Considerations

Understanding what people think about their health provides support for care and qualified education in times of health crises. When analyzed as one of the components of the educational processes developed at the university, health reaffirms the importance of producing care in academic life, demonstrating the relevance of studying and addressing strategies consistent with the development of environments conducive to learning. With this in mind, the students who participated in this research constructed a self-assessment of their health during the COVID-19 pandemic, based on a combination of different factors, such as conceptions and practices related to health, experiences of illness, university life, SARS-CoV-2 prevention measures, and lifestyle. For example, for many students, being ill, experiencing difficulties with distance learning, or distancing themselves from physical activity, to name a few, contributed to a poor perception of their health status. Positive health perceptions, in turn, considered the absence of health problems, adherence to coronavirus prevention practices, return to face-to-face academic activities, and healthy lifestyle habits.

The self-assessed health of these students emphasizes individual aspects of life, with little mention of collective content. Since some components of the participants' self-assessment point to biomedical understandings of health, this might be a sign of the reproduction of the hegemony of this rationality in Western culture. On the other hand, the fact that the students were asked to assess their state of health may have helped them to neglect the influence of macro-social processes in their statements. In addition, the pandemic and the resulting social isolation may have stimulated individual views and care practices. Nevertheless, this is an unclear issue in the self-rated health responses in this survey. COVID-19 has redefined lifestyles and exacerbated inequalities, with implications for the social

determination of health. In Brazil, as in other countries of the global South, the health emergency has triggered a deepening of social, political, and economic problems to a significant degree, problems that are not different from the experience of health and illness during this period because they have been permeated by isolation, contagion, and death through COVID-19.

The peculiarities observed in the self-rated health of students in this study demonstrate the relevance of continuing research using this analytical construct in different social groups and higher education courses, considering the need to highlight the conditions that contribute to determining health status from different perspectives. In this sense, it is important to continue studying the self-rated health of interdisciplinary bachelor's students as well as other university courses by investigating the shaping of care pathways, training paths, academic choices, professional expectations, and ways of dealing with life and health since the end of the COVID-19 pandemic. If health self-assessment is not static or closed, academic training can be a space to orchestrate critical thinking, address health engagement, and produce ruptures with biomedical conceptions.

Among the limitations of this research, we highlight the fact that the data produced through the interviews with the students took place between November 2021 and October 2022, when the Brazilian pandemic scenario showed greater control of the spread and illness caused by coronavirus compared to that experienced in 2020. Because they were not interviewed at the most critical time of the pandemic, it is possible that the students' reports may have masked, minimized, or altered perceptions of factors related to self-rated health to some extent during this period. During data collection, we also noted the difficulty of scheduling interviews with students. As the university was still in the process of resuming face-to-face academic activities, it turned out that students were not concentrated on campus, which made it necessary to invite them to participate in the survey virtually.

References

ABBAS, Asad *et al.* Perceived coronavirus health risk associated with students' life satisfaction: the role of trust in government policies. **Ciência & Saúde Coletiva**, v. 27, n. 8, p. 2995–3004, 2022. Disponível em: <https://doi.org/10.1590/1413-8123202278.06282021>. Acesso em: 26 abr. 2024.

AMARAL, Enzo Lopes; FRICK, Loriane Trombini. Engajamento acadêmico e saúde mental positiva entre estudantes universitários. **Revista Internacional de Educação Superior**, v. 9, e023022, 2023. Disponível em: <https://doi.org/10.20396/riesup.v9i00.8665450>. Acesso em: 17 jul. 2024.

AMORIM, Luciana Oliveira Alves Bastos; COELHO, Maria Thereza Ávila Dantas; ROCHA, Marcelo Nunes Dourado. Saúde e doença: as concepções dos estudantes. *In*: AMORIM, Luciana Oliveira Alves Bastos; ABREU, Maria Angélica Godinho Mendes; COELHO, Maria Thereza Ávila Dantas (Orgs.). **Saúde na educação superior**: o que estudantes e professores

têm a dizer? Salvador: EDUFBA, 2021. p. 25–38. Disponível em: <https://repositorio.ufba.br/ri/handle/ri/34206>. Acesso em: 28 maio 2024.

ANDRADE, Alice Barone de; AZEREDO, Catarina Machado; PERES, Maria Fernanda Tourinho. Exposição à violência comunitária e familiar e autoavaliação de saúde na população brasileira. **Revista Brasileira de Epidemiologia**, v. 23, E200039, 2020. Disponível em: <https://doi.org/10.1590/1980-549720200039>. Acesso em: 13 abr. 2024.

ARAR, Fabiano Cassaño *et al.* Qualidade de vida e saúde mental de estudantes de Medicina na pandemia da covid-19. **Revista Brasileira de Educação Médica**, v. 41, n. 1, e040, 2023. Disponível em: <https://www.scielo.br/j/rbem/a/tzSLrZmJwnGTxjYkXKmyvxf/>. Acesso em: 2 maio 2024.

BARDIN, Laurence. **Análise de conteúdo**. São Paulo: Edições 70, 2016.

BATISTELLA, Carlos. Abordagens contemporâneas do conceito de saúde. *In*: FONSECA, A. F. (Org.). **O território e o processo saúde-doença**. Rio de Janeiro: EPSJV/FIOCRUZ, 2007. p. 51–86.

BOSI, Maria Lúcia Magalhães; ALVES, Erinaldo Domingos. Distanciamento social em contextos urbanos na pandemia de covid-19: desafios para o campo da saúde mental. **Physis: Revista de Saúde Coletiva**, v. 33, e33007, 2023. Disponível em: <https://www.scielo.org/article/physis/2023.v33/e33007/>. Acesso em: 3 maio 2024.

CAMARGO JR., Kenneth Rochel de. A biomedicina. **Physis: Revista de Saúde Coletiva**, v. 15, n. suppl, p. 177–201, 2005. Disponível em: http://www.scielo.br/scielo.php?script=sci_arttext&pid=S0103-73312005000300009&lng=en&nrm=iso&tlng=pt. Acesso em: 11 jul. 2020.

CANGUILHEM, Georges. **O normal e o patológico**. Rio de Janeiro: Forense Universitária, 1995.

COELHO, Maria Thereza Ávila Dantas *et al.* O que é importante cuidar para manter a boa saúde? Concepções de universitários de um curso superior em saúde. **Revista Psicologia, Diversidade e Saúde**, v. 5, n. 2, p. 176–183, 2016. Disponível em: <https://www5.bahiana.edu.br/index.php/psicologia/article/view/1060>. Acesso em: 19 maio 2024.

COULON, Alain. Le métier d'étudiant: L'entrée dans la vie universitaire. **Educação e Pesquisa**, v. 43, n. 4, p. 1239–1250, 2017. Disponível em: http://www.scielo.br/scielo.php?script=sci_arttext&pid=S1517-97022017000401239&lng=en&nrm=iso&tlng=pt. Acesso em: 23 jun. 2020.

FAYERS, Peter; SPRANGERS, Mirjam. Understanding self-rated health. **The Lancet**, v. 359, n. 9302, p. 187–188, 2002. Disponível em: <https://pubmed.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/11812551/>. Acesso em: 29 dez. 2023.

FYLKESNES, Knut; JAKOBSEN, Monika Dybdahl; HENRIKSEN, Nils Oddbjørn. The value of general health perception in health equity research: a community-based cohort study of long-term mortality risk (Finnmark cohort study 1987–2017). **SSM - Population Health**,

v. 15, p. 100848, 2021. Disponível em: <https://pubmed.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/34195347/>. Acesso em: 10 jan. 2024.

GIL, Jesus David Cortes *et al.* Physical Distancing and Mental Well-Being in Youth Population of Portugal and Brazil during the covid-19 Pandemic. **Portuguese Journal of Public Health**, v. 40, n. 2, p. 91–100, 2022. Disponível em: <https://doi.org/10.1159/000525248>. Acesso em: 25 abr. 2024.

GOMES, Lucélia Maria Lima da Silva *et al.* Saúde mental na universidade: ações e intervenções voltadas para os estudantes. **Educação em Revista**, v. 39, e40310, 2023. Disponível em: <https://doi.org/10.1590/0102-469840310>. Acesso em: 17 jul. 2024.

GUIMARÃES, Maria Beatriz *et al.* As Práticas Integrativas e Complementares no campo da saúde: para uma descolonização dos saberes e práticas. **Saúde e Sociedade**, v. 29, n. 1, e190297, 2020. Disponível em: https://www.scielo.br/scielo.php?pid=S0104-12902020000100314&script=sci_arttext. Acesso em: 2 ago. 2020.

GUNDIM, Vivian Andrade *et al.* Transtornos Mentais Comuns e rotina acadêmica na graduação em Enfermagem: impactos da pandemia de covid-19. **Revista Portuguesa de Enfermagem de Saúde Mental**, n. 27, p. 21–37, 2022. Disponível em: https://scielo.pt/scielo.php?script=sci_arttext&pid=S1647-21602022000100021?script=sci_arttext&pid=S1647-21602022000100021. Acesso em: 30 abr. 2024.

HOTTA, Kiyoshi *et al.* University students' living conditions during the covid-19 pandemic and predictors of their subjective health views: A cross-sectional survey. **Drug Discoveries & Therapeutics**, v. 17, n. 2, 2022.01114, 2023. Disponível em: <https://pubmed.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/37121732/>. Acesso em: 24 abr. 2024.

JYLHÄ, Marja. What is self-rated health and why does it predict mortality? Towards a unified conceptual model. **Social Science & Medicine**, v. 69, n. 3, p. 307–316, 2009. Disponível em: <https://pubmed.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/19520474/>. Acesso em: 29 dez. 2023.

MENDONÇA, Edna Mara; LANZA, Fernanda Moura. Conceito de Saúde e Intersetorialidade: Implicações no Cotidiano da Atenção Primária à Saúde. **Revista Psicologia e Saúde**, v. 13, n. 2, p. 155–164, 2021. Disponível em: <https://doi.org/10.20435/pssa.v13i2.1090>. Acesso em: 6 jul. 2024.

MENEGALDI-SILVA, Catherine *et al.* Saúde mental e recursos de enfrentamento em estudantes universitários brasileiros em tempos de pandemia. **Avaliação: Revista da Avaliação da Educação Superior (Campinas)**, v. 27, n. 3, p. 632–650, 2022. Disponível em: <https://www.scielo.br/j/aval/a/XygxmHShDGtgfz7Vc4QtpHr/>. Acesso em: 24 abr. 2024.

MINAYO, Maria Cecília Souza. **O desafio do conhecimento: pesquisa qualitativa em saúde**. 14. ed. São Paulo: Hucitec, 2014.

MIOTTO, Luiz Paulo *et al.* Dor crônica, ansiedade e sintomas depressivos em estudantes de Enfermagem em tempos de pandemia. **Escola Anna Nery**, v. 26, n. spe, e20210351, 2022. Disponível em: <https://www.scielo.br/j/ean/a/X4CHbGqPGLRcBR4SkKQX4SC>. Acesso em: 1 maio 2024.

NUNES, João. A pandemia de covid-19: securitização, crise neoliberal e a vulnerabilização global. **Cadernos de Saúde Pública**, v. 36, n. 5, e00063120, 2020. Disponível em: <https://www.scielo.br/j/csp/a/sng9pd8tLNdY3cQrDChhqPr/?lang=pt#>. Acesso em: 3 maio 2024.

OLIVEIRA, Denize Cristina; GOMES, Antonio Marcos Tosoli; MARQUES, Sergio Corrêa. Análise estatística de dados textuais na pesquisa das representações sociais: alguns princípios e uma aplicação ao campo da saúde. In: MENIN, Maria Suzana Stefano; SHIMIZU, Alessandra Morais. (Orgs.). **Experiência e representação social**: questões teóricas e metodológicas. São Paulo: Casa do Psicólogo, 2005. p. 157–200.

OLIVEIRA, Eliany Nazaré *et al.* covid-19: Repercussions on the mental health of higher education students. **Saúde em Debate**, v. 46, n. spe1, p. 206–220, 2022. Disponível em: <https://doi.org/10.1590/0103-11042022E114>. Acesso em: 1 maio 2024.

RAMOS, Sérgio Ricardo Freire *et al.* Pandemia da covid-19: um evento traumático para estudantes de Ciências Biológicas e da Saúde? **Revista Brasileira de Educação Médica**, v. 47, n. 1, e036, 2023. Disponível em: <https://www.scielo.br/j/rbem/a/dvYtHYLFGQ3r6MYLKKtCLnq/>. Acesso em: 24 abr. 2024.

ROGOWSKA, Aleksandra *et al.* Satisfaction with life among university students from nine countries: Cross-national study during the first wave of covid-19 pandemic. **BMC Public Health**, v. 21, n. 1, 2262, 2021. Disponível em: <https://pubmed.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/34895179/>. Acesso em: 2 maio 2024.

SANTOS, George Amaral; ALMEIDA FILHO, Naomar de. O currículo oculto nas graduações em saúde: percepção de egressos do Bacharelado Interdisciplinar. In: COELHO, Maria Thereza Ávila Dantas; TEIXEIRA, Carmen Fontes de Souza (Orgs.). **Interdisciplinaridade na educação superior**: o bacharelado em saúde. Salvador: EDUFBA, 2016. p. 283–308. Disponível em: <https://repositorio.ufba.br/handle/ri/16263>. Acesso em: 19 maio 2024.

SCLIAR, Moacyr. História do conceito de saúde. **Physis: Revista de Saúde Coletiva**, v. 17, n. 1, p. 29–41, 2007.

SILVA, Marcelo José Souza e; SCHRAIBER, Lilia Blima; MOTA, André. The concept of health in Collective Health: contributions from social and historical critique of scientific production. **Physis: Revista de Saúde Coletiva**, v. 29, n. 1, e290102, 2019. Disponível em: <https://www.scielo.br/j/physis/a/7jH6HgCBkrmFm7RdwkNRHfm/?lang=pt>. Acesso em: 12 jun. 2024.

SOUSA, Jailson Lopes de *et al.* Marcadores de desigualdade na autoavaliação da saúde de adultos no Brasil, segundo o sexo. **Cadernos de Saúde Pública**, v. 36, n. 5, e00230318, 2020. Disponível em: <https://www.scielo.br/j/csp/a/3RRpDG7tNW4SKZF9sm7cvdJ/?lang=pt>. Acesso em: 13 jan. 2024.

SOUSA, Yuri Sá Oliveira. O Uso do Software Iramuteq: Fundamentos de Lexicometria para Pesquisas Qualitativas. **Estud Pesqui Psicol**, v. 21, n. spe., p. 1541–1560, 2021. Disponível

em: <https://www.e-publicacoes.uerj.br/index.php/revispsi/article/view/64034/40275>. Acesso em: 23 fev. 2022.

SZWARCWALD, Celia Landmann *et al.* Determinantes da autoavaliação de saúde no Brasil e a influência dos comportamentos saudáveis: resultados da Pesquisa Nacional de Saúde, 2013. **Revista Brasileira de Epidemiologia**, v. 18, n. suppl 2, p. 33–44, 2015. Disponível em: <https://www.scielo.br/j/rbepid/a/hYWkgXRJyhPHRDNnrRLmt6j/?lang=pt>. Acesso em: 11 jan. 2024.

SZWARCWALD, Celia Landmann *et al.* Factors affecting Brazilians' self-rated health during the covid-19 pandemic. **Cadernos de Saúde Pública**, v. 37, n. 3, e00182720, 2021. Disponível em: <https://www.scielo.br/j/csp/a/x56Q8NJ8xBb8FPYKJW38VXN/?lang=en>. Acesso em: 29 dez. 2023.

TEIXEIRA, Carmen Fontes de Souza; COELHO, Maria Thereza Ávila Dantas; ROCHA, Marcelo Nunes Dourado. Bacharelado Interdisciplinar: uma proposta inovadora na educação superior em saúde no Brasil. **Ciência & Saúde Coletiva**, v. 18, n. 6, p. 1635–1646, 2013. Disponível em: http://www.scielo.br/scielo.php?script=sci_arttext&pid=S1413-81232013000600015&lng=pt&nrm=iso&tlng=pt. Acesso em: 23 jun. 2020.

VIEIRA, Vera Maria Sérgio de Abreu; TORRENTÉ, Mônica de Oliveira Nunes. Saúde mental e interseccionalidade entre estudantes em uma universidade pública brasileira. **Interface - Comunicação, Saúde, Educação**, v. 26, e210674, 2022. Disponível em: <https://doi.org/10.1590/interface.210674>. Acesso em: 17 jul. 2024.

YUAN, Lulu *et al.* Comorbid anxiety and depressive symptoms and the related factors among international medical students in China during covid-19 pandemic: a cross-sectional study. **BMC Psychiatry**, v. 23, n. 1, 165, 2023. Disponível em: <https://pubmed.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/36918819/>. Acesso em: 2 maio 2024.